

Emotional Intelligence and Motivation on Predictors of Pengajar Muda's Performance in Indonesia Mengajar

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ABSTRACT : This study aims to see the relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation with the performance of Pengajar Muda (Education Improvement Facilitator) Indonesia Mengajar. The effectiveness of those performances has been measured in a community development program. This research has expected to gain a kind of model of education community development program, through pengajarmuda's performance, emotional intelligence, and motivation. This research is quantitative research with a survey. Data has been analyzed through SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Data were collected in a survey using three instruments emotional intelligence, motivation, and worker performance, with the number of respondents as many as 76 pengajarmuda. This research found that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant association with pengajarmuda's performance. A value of Significant is $0,00 < 0,05$ and a correlation coefficient of 0,509 (strong), and the motivation variable has a positive and significant association with pengajarmuda's performance. A value of Significant is $0,00 < 0,05$ and a correlation coefficient of 0,602 (strong).

KEYWORDS—Performance; Emotional Intelligence; Motivation; Community Worker

I. INTRODUCTION

The performance theme is a theme that has been researched quite a lot in various studies, but there are still few studies related to a performance whose research subjects are community workers. Research on employee performance in corporate or government is considered normal because they work professionally and can directly calculate company profits and losses, while research on community worker performance is still minimal even though it is important because it shows the accountability of NGOs to the community and funders, both donors, corporate, or government.

Moreover, NGO of education, according to Zastrow (2010), the education system in a democratic society should create equality and provide equal opportunities for all. Education is one of the focus areas in community worker performance research. Because education is one of the effective channels for vertical social mobility to improve one's welfare in the future.

In the field, at this time the quality of education is still apprehensive. UNDP data (2020) on the ranking of the Human Development Index for age, education, and economy, shows that Indonesia's human development index 2020 is ranked 107th out of 189 countries. Utami (2021) revealed that in terms of literacy, Indonesia ranks 62 out of 70 countries, meaning that Indonesia is ranked 8th in the lowest literacy level. This is based on a survey released by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) conducted by PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) in 2019. In more detail, the education inequality of each region in Indonesia has a large inequality, including Papua Province and DKI Jakarta Province which has the largest difference in inequality in school status, namely 38.38% compared to 2.85% (BPS, 2020).

This shows a significant difference between the state capital province and the easternmost province of Indonesia. With a comparison difference of more than 1.346% (thousand three hundred and forty-six percent). Meanwhile, according to Zastrow (2010), the education system in a democratic society should create equality and provide equal opportunities for all.

In the book *Community Development, Creating Community Alternatives-Vision, Analysis, and Practice* (1997), Jim Ife stated that the concept of empowerment is closely related to two main concepts: the concept of power and the concept of disadvantage. The two main concepts are in line with the condition of Indonesian education and the existence of *Pengajar Muda* (Education Improvement Facilitator), *Indonesia Mengajar* (Indonesian teaching movement).

The first, concept of disadvantage is considering Indonesian Education with other countries, the education of each province in Indonesia itself, and the quantity and quality of teachers in villages and big cities. The second is the concept of power: the potential power of *pengajarmuda* (Education Improvement Facilitator) *Indonesia Mengajar* (Indonesian teaching movement) who are directly involved and present in schools and rural in Indonesia. The development of education in the rural area is expected to be more effective and efficient to increase the productivity of *pengajarmudas'* performance. Performance is defined as what individuals do and don't do based on factors such as quantity and quality of results, timeliness, attendance, and ability to collaborate (Mathis & Jackson, 2006). Performance is a record of the results obtained from activities or work over a certain period (Bernardin, 2003). Performance refers to the level of success in completing tasks and the ability to achieve the goals set, performance is considered good and successful if the expected goals can be achieved (Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly, 1997). Mathis & Jackson (2006:378) said performance includes several elements including the following: 1) Quantity of work; 2) Quality of work; 3) Punctuality; 4) Presence; 5) Ability to cooperate.

Indonesia Mengajar is a non-profit organization that recruits and trains the nation's best young people and sends them to various remote areas of Indonesia to serve as *pengajar Muda* (PM) assigned to the community and elementary schools for one year. *Pengajar Muda* as an education improvement facilitator have the following tasks: 1) Interaction in schools; 2) Community development and 3) Regional involvement (*Indonesia Mengajar*: 2021).

Figure 1. Roles and Sub-roles of Community Work

Source: Jim Ife (2013)

The scope of the role of community worker according to Jim ife (2013) is divided into four namely: the role of facilitator, the role of educators, the role of representation, and the role of technical skills. In this research, the researcher will focus on examining the role of the facilitator and educator.

In addition to the performance of *pengajarmuda*, emotional intelligence is a variable that can explain internally and Robbins & Judge (2015) explained that individual emotional intelligence affects performance levels. Reinforced by Goleman (1999:45) states the most important intelligence in achieving the stars is emotional intelligence. Goleman (1999: 512) also explains emotional intelligence is the ability that includes self-control, self-motivation, and the ability to manage emotions well in oneself and relationships with others.

Meanwhile, according to Patton (2002:11) emotional intelligence is knowing and managing emotions effectively to achieve goals, can build productive relationships, and can achieve success.

Emotional intelligence according to Robbins & Judge (2015: 70) is a person's ability to detect and manage emotional instructions and information. Spencer in Goleman (1999: 44) explains that achievement gives more weight to emotional intelligence than cognitive. Daniel Goleman (1995: 34) also explains that IQ contributes only about 20% of the determinants of a person's success while the other 80% is determined by emotional intelligence and other factors.

Goleman (1999:39) mentions five dimensions of emotional intelligence skills, namely: Self Awareness, Self-management, Motivation, Social Awareness, and Relationship Management. 1) Self Awareness (self-awareness) is knowing one's condition, resources owned, self-preference, and intuition. 2) Self-management (self-regulation) is managing the condition of oneself, impulses, and resources. 3) Motivation (motivation) is an emotional tendency that encourages or facilitates achievement. 4) Social Awareness (empathy) is aware of the feelings of others, the needs of others, and the interests of others. 5) Relationship Management (social skills) is the ability to arouse the desired response of others. Some indicators of emotional intelligence dimensions (Goleman, 1999;513).

Predictors of motivation affect individual performance this is stated by several experts including Rothwell, et al (2000), Robbins 1996 (in Rivai& M. Basri, 2018), Umstot (1988), Expectancy Theory (Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly, 1997), and Mathis & Jackson (2006). Motivation is a desire/drive from within a person that causes that person to act (Mathis & Jackson, 2006). Motivation is not only limited to encouragement from within but also encouragement from outside (Daft, 2006).

The theory of motivation is clarified into two by Gibson, et.al (1997) namely: motivational satisfaction theory and motivational process theory. The theory of motivational satisfaction focuses on factors in individuals that can encourage, maintain, direct, and stop a behavior, consisting of ERG theory (Adelfer), Hierarchy of needs (Maslow), two-factor theory (Herzberg), Theory of learned needs (Mc. Clelland). While process theory is a theory that explains and analyzes how behavior is encouraged, directed, maintained, and dismissed, this theory consists of reinforcement theory (Skinner), motivational justice theory (Adams), expectancy theory (Vroom), and goal setting theory (Locke).

The motivation of pengajarmuda in this study uses the theory of needs developed by David Mc. Clelland. He said that a person with a strong need will be motivated to use appropriate behavior to satisfy that need and that need is learned from society and/or culture (Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly, 1997).Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly (1997) state that the three needs include: 1) Needs for achievement. 2) Needs affiliation. 3) Needs for power.

II. METHOD

This study used research methods conducted quantitatively using primary data. The research was carried out from September to October 2022 involving 79 pengajarmuda Indonesia Mengajar, batch XXII and XXIII who are currently scattered in schools and rural areas from 8 districts in Indonesia. Including TanjungJabung Timur (Jambi Province), Seruyan(Central Kalimantan Province), Boalemo(Gorontalo Province), KepulauanAru (Maluku Province), TelukWondama (West Papua Province), West Nias(North Sumatra Province), North Kayong(West Kalimantan Province), Maybrat(West Papua Province), Sigi (Central Sulawesi Province) and East Seram (Maluku Province).

The collection of questionnaire survey data using a questionnaire through Gform. A total of 76 respondents filled out and or returned the questionnaires sent by the researchers (participation rate of 96.2%). The purpose of this research is to know the relationship between emotional intelligence and self-motivation on the performance of pengajarmuda. The independent variable used is the performance variable and the dependent variable used is emotional intelligence and self-motivation. Data analysis was performed using univariate, bivariate, Spearman's test, and using odds ratio. Univariate test analysis was used as a test to find out how big the level of performance was, and how much emotional intelligence and self-motivation of pengajarmuda. Bivariate analysis was used to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and performance and

motivation and performance. Spearman test analysis is used as a test to determine the strength of the relationship between each variable, namely the relationship between emotional intelligence and performance and motivation with performance. Furthermore, the odds ratio is used as a test to find out how likely the dependent variable is to affect the independent variable.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Emotional Intelligence

The performance level of pengajarmuda seen from the data from the questionnaire survey which was analyzed univariately showed that 27.63 percent of the performance levels of pengajarmuda were in a good category. The performance of pengajarmuda in the sufficient category is the smallest percentage, which is 21.05 percent. Meanwhile, the performance in the poor category or at the lowest category level is 25.00 percent. Pengajarmuda who performed very well were 26.32 percent of the 76 respondents, the second largest after the category of respondents who performed well.

Figure 2. Predictor of Performance (n=76)

Source :Olahanpenelitian, 2022

The performance of pengajarmuda in various placements has not yet reached a state of very good performance, although the percentage of good and very good performers is quite large, which is around 54 percent. The two best and largest categories in terms of percentages. The two categories of medium and poor performers also have a percentage that is not far from the percentage of good and very good performers, which is around 46 percent.

This is probably due to the condition of pengajarmuda XXIII who have not been in assignment for a long time, namely since the beginning of September 2022, they are still in a period of adaptation and adjustment to differences in geographical conditions, cultural customs, and habits of the placement community. Pengajarmuda of XXIII batch are not used to the conditions of all limitations and are different from life in urban areas.

3. 2. Emotional Intelligence

Pengajarmuda who have a very high emotional intelligence category have the largest percentage of the other categories, which is 27.63 percent. The category of high emotional intelligence also has the same percentage as the very high category, which is 27.63 percent. While the other two categories, namely the category of low and medium emotional intelligence, both have a percentage of 22.37 percent.

Figure 3. Predictor of Emotional Intelligence (n=76)
 Sumber :Olahanpenelitian, 2022

This shows that the percentage of pengajarmuda have high and very high emotional intelligence. It can also be interpreted that the ability of pengajarmuda in self-control, self-motivation, and ability to manage emotions is good. Relationship of emotional intelligence with performance. Table 1 shows the relationship between emotional intelligence and performance. Pengajarmuda who have low emotional intelligence and poor performance as well as very good and very high emotional intelligence have the largest percentages, namely 58.8 percent and 47.6 percent, respectively. The category of medium emotional intelligence, the category of the largest percentage of those who perform mediumly. Then the category of high emotional intelligence has the same percentage category, namely 28.6 percent for those who perform mediumly, well, and very well.

Table 1. The relationship between emotional intelligence and performance, (n=76)

		Emotional Intelligence		Total
		Medium	High	
Performance	Medium	25	14	39
		73.5%	33.3%	51.3%
	Good	9	28	37
		26.5%	66.7%	48.7%
Total		34	42	76
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Researcher analysis, 2022

The relationship between emotional intelligence and performance is divided into two categories, namely the medium and high categories for emotional intelligence and the medium and good categories for performance. From table 1 above, we can see that pengajarmuda who have medium emotional intelligence will tend to have medium performance. This is indicated by the percentage of 73.5 percent. This means it is bigger than pengajarmuda who have high emotional intelligence. From table 1 we can also see that those who have good performance are more dominantly owned by pengajarmuda who have high emotional intelligence than medium emotional intelligence, which is 66.7 percent.

The relationship between performance and emotional intelligence in this study, we can see the results that in the category of a very good level of performance there are respondents who have the very high

category of emotional intelligence. Meanwhile, for low emotional intelligence, most respondents have a poor performance category. The results of this study also show that emotional intelligence significantly affects the performance of pengajarmuda and has a strong relationship strength as evidenced by the results of the relationship test analysis with the Spearman Rank test, Sig value (0.00) <0.05 and correlation coefficient value 0.509.

The relationship between emotional intelligence and performance when viewed based on the characteristics of the respondent's gender, we can see that for the male gender the most emotional intelligence obtained is high emotional intelligence, which is 11 respondents or 73.3 percent, and has good performance. Meanwhile, the emotional intelligence of male pengajarmuda who have the medium emotional intelligence or have sufficient performance are mostly owned by pengajarmuda who have medium emotional intelligence, namely 7 respondents or 87.5 percent than those who have high emotional intelligence, namely 4 respondents. or 26.7 percent

Table 2. Relationship between emotional intelligence and performance by gender, (n=76)

Gender			Emotional Intelligence		Total
			Medium	High	
Male	Performance	Medium	7	4	11
			87.5%	26.7%	47.8%
	Good		1	11	12
			12.5%	73.3%	52.2%
	Total		8	15	23
			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Female	Performance	Medium	18	10	28
			69.2%	37.0%	52.8%
	Good		8	17	25
			30.8%	63.0%	47.2%
	Total		26	27	53
			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Total	Performance	Medium	25	14	39
			73.5%	33.3%	51.3%
	Good		9	28	37
			26.5%	66.7%	48.7%
	Total		34	42	76
			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Researcher analysis, 2022

Female pengajarmuda who have a good performance category also have the highest category of high emotional intelligence, which is 63 percent. Meanwhile, female pengajarmuda who have medium performance category are mostly owned by female pengajarmuda who have medium emotional intelligence, which is 69.2 percent. It can be said that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence on the performance of pengajarmuda. The higher the emotional intelligence of pengajarmuda, the better the performance they have, and vice versa, the lower the emotional intelligence of pengajarmuda, the lower their performance.

The Odds Ratio was conducted to analyze the effect of emotional intelligence on performance. The results of the odds ratio test obtained an "Estimate" value of 5.6, with a confidence interval of 95 percent (CI), meaning that pengajarmuda with low emotional intelligence are 5.5 times more likely to have poor performance than those with high emotional intelligence. The values of the Common Odds Ratio Lower Bound and Upper Bound show the upper and lower limits of the odds ratio, which means that at least respondents with low

emotional intelligence are at least 2.1 times more at risk of having poor performance and at most 15.0 times more at risk.

3.2.Motivation

In addition to emotional intelligence, motivation is also assumed to affect the performance of pengajarmuda. The biggest motivation for pengajarmuda in the high motivation category is 32.89 percent. The second largest category of motivation for pengajarmuda is the very high motivation category, which is 27.63 percent. Then 21.05 percent of the percentage value of the category of low motivation. Finally, the category that has the lowest percentage is the medium motivation category, which is 18.42 percent

As seen from table 3, as many as 30.3 percent have medium motivation for pengajarmuda who have medium performance and 9.2 percent have good performance. Meanwhile, pengajarmuda who have high motivation and have good motivational performance are 39.5 percent, and pengajarmuda who have high motivation and have sufficient motivational performance are 21.1 percent.

Table 3. The relationship between motivation and performance, (n=76)

		Motivation		Total
		Medium	High	
Performance	Medium	23	16	39
		30.3%	21.1%	51.3%
	Good	7	30	37
		9.2%	39.5%	48.7%
Total		30	46	76
		39.5%	60.5%	100.0%

Source: Researcher analysis, 2022

From table 3, we can see the relationship between motivation and performance with two categories, namely the medium and good category for the performance variable and the medium and high category for the motivation variable. From table 3 we can see that pengajarmuda who have high motivation will tend to perform well, this is indicated by the percentage value of 39.5 percent. The percentage value is greater than that of pengajarmuda who have adequate performance, which is only 9.2 percent.

The results of this study also show that motivation significantly affects the performance of pengajarmuda and has a strong relationship strength as evidenced by the relationship analysis test of the Spearman Rank test, the test results show that getting significant results, namely the Sig value (0.00) <0.05 and the coefficient value correlation 0.602.

Odds Ratio analysis or risk test is conducted to analyze the influence of motivation on performance. The results of the odds ratio analysis/risk test are the "Estimate" value of 6.161 with a Confidence Interval (CI) value of 95 percent, meaning that respondents who have low motivation are 6.1 times more likely to have low performance than respondents who have high motivation.

The upper and lower limits of the odds ratio are indicated by the values of the lower bound and upper bound common odds ratios. This means that at least respondents with low emotional intelligence are at least 2.1 times more at risk of having poor performance and at most are 15.0 times more at risk.

The values of the Common Odds Ratio Lower Bound and Upper Bound indicate the upper and lower limits of the OR, meaning that pengajarmuda respondents who have low motivation are at least 2.2 times more at risk, have adequate performance, and are at most 17.4 times more at risk.

Table 4. The relationship between motivation and performance by gender, (n=76)

Gender	Performance	Motivation	Motivation		Total
			Medium	High	
Male	Performance	Medium	4	7	11
		Good	3	9	12
	Total		7	16	23
			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Female	Performance	Medium	19	9	28
		Good	4	21	25
	Total		23	30	53
			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Total	Performance	Medium	23	16	39
		Good	7	30	37
	Total		30	46	76
			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Researcher analysis, 2022

The relationship between motivation and performance is seen based on the gender characteristics of the respondents. We can see that for the male sex the most motivated are 9 respondents, namely 56.3 percent who have high performance. For pengajarmuda who are male, the most dominant performance is felt by pengajarmuda who have medium motivation, namely 4 respondents, amounting to 57.1 percent.

Pengajarmuda who are female and have good performance are mostly pengajarmuda who have high motivation 21 respondents, namely 70 percent. Pengajarmuda who have medium performance is also felt by pengajarmuda who have medium motivation, namely 82.6 percent. For pengajarmuda, both male and female, it can be said that there is a positive relationship between motivation and level of performance, where the higher the motivation, the better the performance of pengajarmuda.

IV. CONCLUSION

The performance of pengajarmuda in the rural area of various districts has the largest percentage in the category of good performers. The emotional intelligence variable found that there was a significant relationship between the emotional intelligence variable (dependent) and the performance variable (independent), and the direction of the relationship was positive. Furthermore, the motivation variable (second dependent variable) also has a significant relationship and the direction of the positive relationship with the independent variable/performance.

The higher the emotional intelligence, the better the performance of pengajarmuda, this also applies to pengajarmuda, both male and female. Higher motivation makes the performance of pengajarmuda better, this also applies to pengajarmuda, both male and female, the positive relationship between motivation and performance is stronger for female pengajarmuda. Emotional intelligence and motivation of pengajarmuda affect the performance of pengajarmuda. When emotional intelligence is high, the performance will be even better. And when the motivation is high, the performance will be even better and vice versa.

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